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Economics of Big Science

REPORT

PRELIMINARY SOCIO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF SELECTED IMPACT PATHWAYS OF THE BEAMLINER FOR SCHOOLS PROGRAMME

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Executive Summary

This report presents a first and preliminary quantitative socio-economic impact analysis of the CERN coordinated Beamline for Schools (BL4S) programme. Using records, survey data, and cost-benefit analysis methods, this study estimates the values of selected impact pathways including skill development, public engagement, institutional spillovers, travel-related value, labour inputs, and digital outreach. The analysis uses EU, OECD, and EIB methods and guidelines and considers uncertainties. All present values are expressed in 2025 prices using social discounting.

With respect to student skill development, the study revealed significant positive changes from before to after the competition across eight skill areas and five attitudinal measures. A positive change on all eight skills was observed with the largest effect (+0.80) in scientific writing, followed by designing an experiment (+0.79).

The scientific and technical output production was monetised based on 5 recorded peer-reviewed publications. Based on the shadow price of 300 author-hours/paper and an apprentice-level subsistence of 4.26 CHF/hr the conservative production value corresponds to about CHF 6,390.

The travel-related value of the on-site participation of the winning teams based on airfare, travel-time and 14-day on site stay, monetised using an individual Travel Cost Method with additional consumer surplus corresponds to about €206,700 (CHF 194,191) for the 2023 to 2025 period. A forecast for the period 2026 to 2030 (4 years) yields a conservatively estimated value of about €898,300 (CHF 844,377).

The programme labour input relating to engaged staff and volunteers using a salary-based shadow price estimate at a midpoint of 62.2 CHF/hr leads to an estimated value of about CHF 133,400 per year (\approx €141,900). A forecast for the 2026 to 2030 period represents a present value of CHF 610,900 at a social discount rate of 3%, CHF 602,300 at 3.5% and 593,900 at 4%.

The value of digital outreach and public engagement was estimated based on 231 recorded social media posts and videos on 7 platforms. 602,739 views, 70,078 engagements were monetised using the earned media value method for which attention-time was multiplied with an average leisure-time value. The midpoint estimate corresponds to a value of about €351,100 (CHF 330,016). For this impact pathway also a Monte Carlo simulation was carried out to reveal uncertainties. The simulated mean value is €296,000 (CHF 278,240) with a 90% interval leading to a value range of €213,000 to €403,000, in line with the initial midpoint estimate.

The results of this first, preliminary analysis of a selected set of socio-economic impact pathways of the BL4S competition provides evidence for the observation of positive effects on scientific competencies acquisition, confidence increase, and long-term strengthening of STEM engagement. This study provides a transparent, replicable evidence base for continued studies to elucidate the socio-economic value of the BL4S programme.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. BEAMLIN FOR SCHOOLS

The Beamline For Schools (BL4S) [5] programme is an international competition for high-school students, coordinated by CERN (Geneva, Switzerland) in collaboration with DESY (the German Electron Synchrotron, Hamburg, Germany) and the ELSA accelerator (University of Bonn, Germany). Launched in 2014, the competition invites teams of secondary-school students to design an experiment that can be carried out on the beam of a particle accelerator, that is, a stream of particles of the kind normally used in professional research. Teams submit a written proposal, and the authors of the selected entries win a trip to one of the host laboratories, where they run their experiment at a beamline alongside professional physicists [26].

CERN provides the overall framework, mentorship and online training, while DESY and the University of Bonn act as additional host sites for the practical work. In the current configuration, five winning teams are hosted each year: two at CERN, two at DESY and one at ELSA [27]. Proposals are assessed by a committee of CERN, DESY and ELSA scientists, who select the winners from a shortlist. Beyond the on-site experience, BL4S gives participating teams access to analysis tools, datasets and mentoring webinars, so that teams that are not selected also have access to these resources, and a further set of teams receives recognition awards, such as telescopes from the “Stars shine for everyone” project.

Participation has changed over the period covered in this study: from 380 teams in 2023 to 508 in 2025, with 712 submissions recorded in the 2026 cycle, involving over 4,500 students from 89 countries [25]. This participation spans both high-income and middle-income regions, which is relevant to the socio-economic evaluation set out in the rest of this report.

1.2. AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to quantify, in monetary terms where possible, selected socio-economic impacts generated by the Beamline for Schools programme through an analysis of a set of impact pathways, following the Theory of Change approach. Rather than attempting a complete cost-benefit account of the programme, the analysis concentrates on pathways for which data are available and for which established valuation methods can be applied: student skill development, scientific and technical output, the travel-related value of on-site participation, programme labour inputs, and digital outreach. For each pathway, the study draws on methods from the cost-benefit analysis literature on research infrastructures, including shadow pricing, the Travel Cost Method, and attention-time valuation, and reports results in 2025 prices. The purpose is to provide a transparent and reproducible evidence base that can support later and more complete evaluations of the programme, and to indicate the order of magnitude of the value associated with each pathway. The study does not set out to establish a single overall benefit-cost ratio, nor to measure long-term effects on participants’ careers or earnings.

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The analysis is guided by the following research questions:

1. What socio-economic value can be attributed to the selected BL4S impact pathways, expressed in monetary terms where the data and methods allow?
2. Which valuation methods from the research-infrastructure cost-benefit literature can be applied to each pathway, given the programme data that are available?
3. What changes in self-reported scientific self-efficacy or self-confidence do participants record between the start and the end of the programme, and how do these differ across resource settings?
4. How does the estimated value of the travel-related and pathways compare with the programme's reported annual budget?
5. How sensitive are the estimates to the main assumptions, in particular the social discount rate and the parameters used in the travel-cost and media-value models?

Together, these questions cover the measurement of value, the choice of method, the participant-level outcomes, the comparison with programme cost, and the treatment of uncertainty.

1.4. SCOPE, BOUNDARIES AND LIMITATIONS

The analysis covers the competition cycles from 2023 to 2025 for the full set of outcomes and includes the 2026 cycle for participation and application indicators. For pathways that involve recurring annual flows, values are projected to 2030. All monetary values are expressed in 2025 prices, using GDP deflators for comparison, and future values are discounted using social discount rates of 3.0%, 3.5% and 4.0%, in line with European appraisal guidance. Figures are reported in Swiss francs and euros, converted at 1 EUR = 0.94 CHF (ECB, end-2024). The programme's indicative annual budget, used as a reference, is circa CHF 230,000.

Geographically, the study considers participating teams from the countries represented in the application records, together with the three host laboratories at which on-site activities take place: CERN in Geneva, DESY in Hamburg, and ELSA in Bonn. Travel-related estimates are based on routes between participant countries and these host sites.

The empirical basis consists of the BL4S application records for 2023 to 2025, a participant survey with 369 valid responses collected in 2026, and supplementary datasets for travel costs and media coverage. Team-level and individual-level statistics are reported against separate denominators and are not combined. The datasets used in this study, together with their coverage, preparation, quality checks and limitations, are described in full in Chapter 3: Data Sources and Data Quality.

The study assesses six impact components. Four are expressed in monetary terms:

1. scientific and technical output,
2. travel-related value of on-site participation,
3. programme labour inputs, and
4. digital outreach.

Skill development is reported through descriptive or survey-based indicators rather than monetary values.

Institutional spillovers, participation and diversity are reported descriptively.

The estimates use shadow pricing, the Travel Cost Method, and an attention-time model for digital outreach; they rely on market proxies and stated or revealed preferences rather than direct market prices, so the figures should be read as approximations.

Several elements were not included in the analysis: It does not estimate long-term effects on participants' education or earnings, and it does not produce a single overall benefit-cost ratio. Labour inputs are valued only on the CERN side; staff time contributed by DESY and the University of Bonn is not captured. Costs and benefits attributed to sponsors and to the wider regional economy are included only where noted. Airfare and on-site cost figures are based on public fare aggregators and published subsistence rates rather than actual participant bookings, and several behavioural parameters are taken from earlier studies of CERN visitors rather than from BL4S participants.

The presented results are therefore to be considered preliminary and are intended to support further work rather than provide an exhaustive evaluation.

2. ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT PATHWAYS

This study analysis quantitatively four socio-economic impact pathways through which Beamline for Schools (BL4S) may generate measurable value beyond its direct educational purpose.

1) Scientific and Technical Output: This pathway values the knowledge capital generated by the production of publications. Rather than utilizing long-term bibliometric lag metrics, it applies an input-cost shadow-pricing model based on the specialized intellectual labour hours invested during production. For the baseline analysis, a pool of 5 recorded peer-reviewed publications is valued at a fixed effort of 300 author-hours per publication. Utilizing a geographically blended and inflation-adjusted apprentice-level labour rate of 4.26 CHF/hour, the baseline value of the generated knowledge capital is calculated at 6,390 CHF.

2) Travel-related value of on-site participation: BL4S creates expenditure effects when winning teams travel to CERN, DESY, and ELSA. These effects include transport, accommodation, food, local mobility, and accompanying-person expenses. In the Travel Cost Method calculation, the 2025 cycle is valued using 56 visitors, consisting of 51 team members and 5 parents. The weighted average direct travel cost is estimated at €1,792 per person, giving total direct travel expenditure of about €100,352. The consumer surplus estimate is €1,195 per person, or about €66,920 in total. With the regional multiplier component, the total travel-related value is estimated at about €251,356. The analysis of this pathway is limited to the smaller group of winning teams and accompanying visitors, and it gives a monetary estimate of local spillovers from on-site scientific participation.

3) Programme Labour Inputs: This pathway establishes a shadow price for the intellectual labour embedded in delivering BL4S, using official salary scales rather than direct market transactions. Calibrated against an official CERN vacancy notice for BL4S experimental support, the model scales net stipends to total employer costs by adjusting for internal tax structure and an employer pension contribution. This derived hourly shadow value provides an independent benchmark for the programme's indicative annual budget of about CHF 230,000 and values the hours contributed by operational roles alongside voluntary student, fellow, and data-analysis contributions calculated at 30- and 50-hour midpoints.

4) Digital Outreach: This pathway measures public attention and engagement metrics via online channels. It quantifies the digital footprint and attention-time valuation generated by the programme's digital presence, analyzing components such as social media posts, videos, impressions, and views. Platform-specific attention-time parameters are applied to reported exposure and engagement figures to derive total audience attention hours, which are then monetised using a standard leisure-time value benchmark of EUR 12.97 per hour.

2.2. THEORY OF CHANGE ANALYSIS

The Theory of Change (ToC) analysis for BL4S follows a causal chain from inputs to activities, to outputs, to outcomes, and finally to impacts. At the input stage, BL4S combines CERN, DESY, ELSA, school, teacher, student, donor, and industry resources. The ToC table records an indicative programme budget of about CHF 250,000, subject to update, 30 expert scientists as evaluators, dedicated staff at CERN, DESY, and ELSA, training materials in safety and scientific software, and in-kind scientific equipment. These inputs create the conditions for high-school teams to participate in a real research process rather than only a classroom exercise.

The activity stage consists of the work carried out by students, coaches, scientists, and partner institutions. Students and coaches spend time researching scientific problems and writing experimental proposals. The table separates this into approximately 110 hours of structured technical training, 10 hours of online training in safety, data-taking, and analysis, continuous online mentorship from CERN scientists, and a 14-to-15-day onsite presence for winning teams at CERN, DESY, and ELSA. Activities also include proposal evaluation by around 30 scientists per cycle, real beamline data-taking, software-based analysis using the ROOT analysis software and Python, publication or presentation of results, press communication, and social media outreach.

The output stage covers the direct results of these activities. On the educational side, the programme produces submitted proposals, selected winning teams, trained students and coaches, beamline experiments, and teacher-facing materials. Official participation figures show the output scale increasing from 379 proposals in 2023 to 712 submissions in 2026. In the uploaded workbook, returning-team continuity is visible in the application data: the prior-participation rate increased from 36.3% in 2023 to 38.4% in 2024 and 53.3% in 2025. On the scientific-output side, the ToC identifies BL4S-listed student publications, experimental datasets, conference presentations, infographics, diagrams, and outreach materials.

The outcome stage refers to changes after the direct BL4S activity. These include improved familiarity with particle physics, teacher use of laboratory equipment, creation of STEM clubs or follow-up projects, and wider school engagement. The 2026 survey records 223 of 278 completed coach responses, or 80.2%, selecting “support another BL4S team in the future.” The impact stage then links these outcomes to longer-term effects: human-capital formation in STEM, university admission prospects, public science awareness, institutional investment in science education, local tourism expenditure, and potential labour-market contributions from students who later enter scientific or technical careers.

2.3. VALUATION APPROACH

The valuation approach combines a theory-based impact framework with partial cost-benefit analysis. The ToC analysis defines the causal sequence to be tested: BL4S inputs, such as beamline access opportunity, scientific staff time, training materials and funding, lead to activities such as proposal writing, online mentoring, technical training and on-site experiments. These activities generate measurable outputs, including student proposals, selected teams, publications, datasets, media outputs and teacher follow-up activities. The quantitative part of the study then estimates selected effects where monetary or numerical proxies are available.

The study does not attempt to monetise every possible impact of BL4S. It focuses on pathways for which the available data allow transparent measurement: travel-related value for winning teams, scientific and technical output, programme labour input, digital outreach, and selected human-capital and institutional indicators. For the travel component, the Travel Cost Method is used because the on-site experience at CERN, DESY or ELSA is not sold at a market price. The model therefore uses observed or estimated travel expenditure, accommodation, daily costs and accompanying-person costs as a proxy for the minimum revealed value of participation.

For non-market outputs, the study applies shadow pricing. This is used for scientific publications, student or teacher time, and programme labour inputs where no direct market transaction exists.

2.4. RELATIONSHIP TO SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT

The analytical design follows the logic of established socio-economic appraisal standards for public investment and research infrastructure assessment. The DG REGIO Cost-Benefit Analysis Guide and the 2021–2027 Economic Appraisal Vademecum define project appraisal as a comparison of social costs and social benefits, including non-market effects where market prices do not capture welfare value. This is relevant for BL4S because many outputs, such as student research experience, public engagement and scientific learning, are not traded in markets. The OECD reference framework for research infrastructures is also relevant because it recommends tracing scientific and socio-economic impacts through indicators adapted to the type and lifecycle stage of the infrastructure. The European Commission Better Regulation framework is reflected in the distinction between inputs, outputs, outcomes and impacts, and in the use of proportionate evidence. Effects are monetised only where an explicit valuation method is available; otherwise, they are reported as physical or survey-based indicators.

For the 2026–2030 projection period, recurring benefits and costs are discounted to present value using standard Social Discount Rate scenarios. The baseline sensitivity range uses 3.0%, 3.5% and 4.0%.

3. DATA SOURCES AND DATA QUALITY

3.1. DATA INVENTORY

The empirical foundation for the socio-economic impact evaluation in this study relies on application records and follow-up questionnaires administered by the BL4S programme organisation. To support transparency of empirical evidence and clarify data provenance, Table 1 compiles the core structured datasets processed throughout the analytical pipeline. Besides the two core datasets, this study also adopts two supplementary datasets for travel-cost valuation and media value analysis. These auxiliary data are independently collected to assess extended socio-economic impacts, while administrative records and questionnaires remain the primary evidence base.

Table 1: Summary of Core and Supplementary Empirical Datasets for BL4S Source: CERN/BL4S administrative records.

Dataset	Period	Unit	Observations
Application Records	2023–2025	Team	1,233 teams (~9,000 students)
Questionnaire	2023–2026	Individual	478 (369 valid)
Travel Data	Multi-year	Route / Participant	24 routes, 84 persons
Media Data	Multi-year	Post / Impression	200+ items

As presented in the table above, the analytical framework is built upon two interconnected databases. The first is the multi-year BL4S application records covering the competition cycles from 2023 to 2025, with a total of 1,233 teams. Prior to automated data cleaning and deduplication, the records for each year are summarised as follows:

- 2023 (10th edition): 380 raw entries, corresponding to 379 valid proposals, representing over 2,500 high school students from 68 countries.
- 2024 (11th edition): 461 complete proposals from over 3,000 students across 78 countries.
- 2025 (12th edition): 508 complete proposals from over 3,500 students across 72 countries.

The records contain information regarding geographical distribution, country coverage, cross-year participation trends, and gender composition. They provide an empirical foundation for the accessibility analysis.

The second dataset is the BL4S impact evaluation questionnaire collected via SurveyHero in 2026. A total of 478 response sessions were initially captured. To establish a quality estimation framework, a row-wise completeness filter was applied to exclude incomplete or abandoned responses. After screening, 369 fully completed questionnaires were retained, representing a 77.2% completion rate. The remaining 109 incomplete records are classified as standard sample attrition. These 369 validated observations including multidimensional psychometric scores, behavioural intention items and local cost data, form the empirical basis for estimating participant behavioural changes in this study.

In this study, "confidence" is operationally defined as participants' subjective self-efficacy regarding specific academic and technical competencies required by the BL4S program. Rather than representing a general psychological state, it quantifies a student's self-assessed capability to independently execute distinct scientific tasks such as data analysis, programming, and experimental design, measured before and after the competition.

In addition to the above records, two categories of supplementary data are utilised to conduct extended economic and outreach impact assessment. The first set focuses on travel-related expenses of winning teams, while the second collects digital content metrics for media value calculation.

3.2. TRAVEL COST DATASETS

The travel-cost evaluation incorporates publicly available datasets tracking airfares, on-site expenses, leisure time value, and economic discount indicators. Airfare benchmarks were sampled from Skyscanner in December 2025 across eight origin countries and three potential host destinations (CERN Geneva, DESY Hamburg, and ELSA Bonn). Participant counts per winning team were cross-referenced with CERN Indico logs, team proposals, and institutional press releases. On-site daily expenses were estimated based on a baseline CERN subsistence rate of 92 CHF/person/day (equivalent to approximately €95.00/day, yielding €1,330 for a standard 14-day stay), aligned with the main report discussion and deflated for prior years using HICP series. The value of leisure time (VLT) reflects a blended average of seven transport-economics studies, while a Social Discount Rate of 3% is applied to the 2026–2030 projections.

Table 2: Detailed Inventory of Travel-Cost Datasets.

Dataset	Source	Period	Unit
Airfare Estimates	Skyscanner (December 2025)	2023–2025	Route–lab pair
Team Participant Lists	CERN Indico, team proposals, press	2023–2025	Travelling participant
Daily On-Site Expense	CERN	2025 base, 2023–24 adjusted	€/person/day
Value of Leisure Time (VLT)	EC DG MOVE, Wardman et al.	2021 base	€/hour
GDP Deflator & SDR	Eurostat, ECB, EIB, UNIMI-LHC	2021–2030	Index/rate

3.3. MEDIA VALUE DATASETS

Apart from travel data, this research also compiles digital media data to quantify the outreach influence of BL4S. Relevant content was manually gathered from mainstream social platforms operated by CERN, BL4S and their partner institutions. Data recorded includes basic content information, user engagement data and industry-standard time benchmarks to calculate overall earned media value. The specific media datasets are summarised in the following table.

Table 3: Detailed Inventory of Media Value Datasets.

Dataset	Source	Period	Unit
Social Media Records	Manual collection	2014 - 2026	Posts/Videos
Engagement Aggregates	Derived from raw records	2025 - 2026	Platform Aggregate
Attention-Time Benchmarks	Improvado, Hootsuite, DataReportal	2021 - 2025	Seconds/view
Value of Leisure Time (VLT)	EC DG MOVE, Wardman et al.	2021 base	€/hour

3.4. UNIT OF ANALYSIS

To address potential aggregation bias and resolve ambiguities in hierarchical structure, this study establishes two distinct, non-overlapping levels of observation for core analysis. Different analytical units are defined for supplementary travel and media evaluation. The classification of analytical units is presented below.

Table 4: General Unit of Analysis by Component.

Analysis component	Unit of analysis
Participation by country	Team or student
Gender composition	Student
Skill development	Student survey response
Institutional spillovers	School or coach response
Travel-cost valuation	Travelling participant or winning team
Publication valuation	Publication count per year
Labour-input valuation	Staff role / person-hour
Digital outreach	Post, video, impression or view

The Team Level is applied to the assessment of geographical diversity, national coverage, and program application trends. The underlying unit of observation is a single, deduplicated team application record. The statistical denominator is anchored at independent team records merged across the 2023–2025 competition cycles.

The Individual Student Level is deployed for the micro-level analysis of core competency transfer and outcome assessment. The unit of analysis is restricted to independent questionnaire response vectors. To prevent incomplete responses from distorting the results, all student-level statistics use the $n = 369$ questionnaires that were fully completed and matched across the self-efficacy and behavioural-intention measures.

For supplementary assessment items, separate analytical units are adopted according to research objectives. Travel cost analysis focuses on winning teams and their travelling members, while media evaluation takes individual online posts and videos as basic units. Detailed unit settings for travel and media modules are shown in two separate tables.

Table 5: Unit of Analysis — Travel-Cost Components.

Analysis component	Unit of analysis
Travel-cost valuation	Travelling participant
Airfare component	Route-lab pair
On-site expense component	Person-day
Time cost component	Travel-hour per participant
Consumer surplus	Participant
Forecast (2026–2030)	Year-cohort

The analytical unit settings for travel-cost valuation are tailored to the economic assessment of in-person programme participation, with each unit corresponding to a specific cost component and valuation dimension. In parallel, the media value analysis adopts a distinct set of analytical units that align with the characteristics of digital content and online engagement, ensuring that the measurement of outreach impact is methodologically consistent with the analytical framework of this study.

Table 6: Unit of Analysis — Media Value Components.

Analysis component	Unit of analysis
Impression count	View / impression
Engagement count	Like, comment, or share
Attention time	Second of attention per platform
Earned Media Value (EMV)	€ per platform
Monte Carlo uncertainty	Simulated total EMV draw

By implementing a methodological stratification, this report aligns reported percentages and statistical means to the denominator appropriate to each level: team-level figures to the count of team records, and student-level figures to the validated questionnaire responses so that the two levels are never combined in a single statistic. This approach reduces data cross-contamination and maintains consistent measurement standards, supporting the consistency of the evaluation.

3.5. DATA PREPARATION AND CLEANING

To address structural differences across data sources and platforms, a unified data cleaning pipeline was developed using the Pandas and NumPy libraries in Python. Core processing rules for administrative and questionnaire data are summarised in the following table.

Table 7: Data Cleaning and Transformation Procedures.

Raw Data Source	Issue	Cleaning Procedure
Registration Forms (2023–2025)	Duplicate column names causing structural misalignment	Standardised column naming; merged datasets into a unified panel
Questionnaire 2026 (Before/After Items)	Text-based qualitative responses (non-numeric)	Converted to 1.0–5.0 Likert scale values using a mapping dictionary
Numerical Fields (e.g., hours)	Statistical outliers from response variance	Truncated at defined thresholds to reduce noise
Travel & Media Data	Format inconsistency / missing view data	Unified structure + placeholder assignment

Note: Final processed datasets contain 1,233 team records (18 columns) and 369 valid individual responses.

This code-driven cleaning process limits manual adjustment errors and establishes a structured foundation for subsequent quantitative analysis. Apart from core datasets, targeted structural harmonization, HICP-based currency deflation, and parameter alignment were conducted on exogenous travel logs and digital media data to resolve cross-platform discrepancies.

For travel datasets: Since no single source contains both participant figures and travel costs, datasets were merged by country–year–laboratory keys. Where participant numbers conflicted across sources, conservative values were adopted. For teams with unconfirmed host laboratories, average fares across the three labs were used. All airfare and on-site expenses were deflated using HICP indices for 2023 and 2024 sourced from Eurostat and the ECB.

For media datasets: Raw content was manually compiled and grouped by platform. Since certain platforms do not release public view counts, uniform placeholder values and attention-time thresholds were applied using industry conversion benchmarks extracted from Hootsuite (2025), DataReportal/GWI (2024), and Improvado (2024). No deflation was conducted for media engagement data, and the VLT parameter remains consistent with the travel module.

3.6. MISSING DATA AND EXCLUSIONS

Exclusion of Incomplete Survey Sessions

A total of 109 entries were identified as incomplete sessions due to mid-survey abandonment or non-submission. These records lacked values across core pre-test and post-test indicators, exhibiting a Missing Completely at Random (MCAR) pattern. To avoid biased statistical inference, these 109 records were excluded from the analysis.

Final Valid Sample

Following this screening, 369 fully completed questionnaires were retained, yielding a 77.2% completion rate.

For the 2023–2025 registration dataset covering 1,233 teams, the administrative records are complete regarding macro-level geographical and gender attributes, requiring no further exclusions. With consistent cleaning and exclusion criteria, a consistent sample baseline is established for further analysis.

In addition, we also checked missing values and data limitations for travel and media supplementary data and adopted reasonable handling strategies accordingly.

Missing Data in Travel and Media Datasets

Two gaps exist in travel data: some winning teams have no confirmed host laboratory, and supervisor numbers are not fully recorded in public materials. We adopted average fares and assumed 2 supervisors per team following BL4S rules; no travel records were excluded. For media data, Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn do not display public view counts, which leads to partial under-estimation of reach. All collected media posts and videos were retained without removal.

3.7. DATA QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Following data preparation, a technical quality check evaluated the final analytical dataset across two dimensions: uniqueness and logical consistency. The assessment covers both core and supplementary data to ensure overall reliability.

Uniqueness and Record Integrity

Duplicate verification performed on the merged 2023–2025 team registration dataset confirmed no repeated team entries across submission cycles. For the survey sample, verifying the global uniqueness of the Respondent_ID identifier indicated no duplicate submissions.

Multivariate Logical Consistency Check

Automated validation applied to the paired variables, including BEFORE_Conf_ and AFTER_Conf_, confirmed that all observations fell within the designated 1.0 - 5.0 Likert range, with no out-of-bound records. Skewness testing on the working-hour variable Hours_Time verified that extreme values from data entry errors were addressed through threshold trimming. All monetary and time values in travel and media data fall within reasonable logical ranges.

3.8. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE ANALYSED DATASETS

This section outlines the descriptive statistics for key variables after data cleaning, serving as the foundation for the empirical tests and quantitative modelling. We first present statistical results for core participant and competency indicators.

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Core Survey Variables.

Variable	Respondents	Mean	Std Dev	Min	Max
Num_Students (Team size)	369	6.67	4.29	0.0	50.0
BEFORE_Conf_Total (Pre-program total confidence)	369	3.64	0.73	1.08	5.00
AFTER_Conf_Total (Post-program total confidence)	369	4.15	0.62	1.23	5.00
Hours_Time (Total project mentoring hours)	369	50.33	33.15	0.0	100.0
NPS (Net Promoter Score)	369	8.61	1.83	0.0	10.0

As indicated in Table 8, the average team size is approximately 6.67 students. The minimum value of 0.0 for Num_Students and Hours_Time reflects valid survey responses rather than missing or erroneous data: these rows were retained because they contain complete and valid responses on the other core evaluative variables (such as NPS and confidence scores), and excluding them would have reduced the survey sample size without improving data quality. The Net Promoter Score (NPS) is a loyalty metric with values between 0 (unlikely to recommend) and 10 (likely to recommend) that measures how likely people are to recommend a company, product, service, or experience to others.

Table 8 reports a mean NPS-question score of 8.61 out of 10 across all 369 respondents. Using the standard Net Promoter methodology (promoters minus detractors), the subset of 321 respondents with a valid 0 to 10 score corresponds to a Net Promoter Score of 54.8, with 64.5% classified as promoters (score 9-10), 25.9% as passives (score 7-8), and 9.7% as detractors (score 0-6).

Figure 1: Coach Net Promoter Score (NPS) distribution and classification, 2026 survey (n = 321).

Next, we provide descriptive statistics for travel-cost and media-related indicators, which support the socio-economic impact analysis.

Table 9: Descriptive Statistics of Travel-Cost Variables

Variable	Observations	Mean / value	Min	Max
On-site participants per year-cohort	3 years	28.3	23 (2024)	33 (2025)
Round-trip airfare / person (€, 2025)	24 routes	€681	€90	€900
Round-trip travel time (hrs, 2025)	24 routes	13.4	1.3	24.5
Daily on-site expense / person (€)	3 cities	€101.50	€70	€101.50
14-day on-site cost / person (€)	-	€1,421	-	-
Value of leisure time (€/hr)	7 sources	€12.97	€6.72	€17.20
Total annual travel value (€, nominal)	3 years	€67,863	€50,552	€96,978
Total discounted value (2026–2030)	5 years	€444,126	€83,654	€94,153

Beyond the direct economic value associated with on-site participation, this study also quantifies the digital outreach and communication impact of the BL4S programme through social media metrics. The following table presents descriptive statistics for key digital engagement and media value indicators, which complement the travel cost analysis to form a comprehensive assessment of the programme’s socio-economic footprint.

Table 10: Descriptive Statistics of Digital Outreach Variables covering the period 2014 to 2026.

Variable	Observations	Mean / total	Min	Max
Impressions YouTube	17 videos	114,567	780	17,000
Impressions YouTube Shorts	11 videos	18,331	108	11,629
Impressions X (Twitter)	10 posts	368,712	1	199,000
Impressions TikTok	9 videos	100,756	1,056	59,000
Total attention time (seconds)	7 platforms	82,230,994	82,147,897	82,284,008
Value of leisure time (€/hr)	7 sources	€12.97	€6.72	€17.20
Total EMV (€, average scenario)	7 platforms	€296,260	€295,961	€296,451
CERN video portal views	30 videos	55.5	3	458

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. PARTICIPATION, DIVERSITY AND ACCESS INDICATORS

This component measures the extent to which BL4S reaches students from different countries, educational contexts, and demographic groups. The objective is to describe participation patterns and access to the programme using harmonised indicators derived from application and survey datasets covering 2023–2026.

The unit of analysis varies by indicator and is reported explicitly to avoid aggregation bias. Team-level indicators are used for proposal submissions and participation rates, while student-level indicators are used for demographic characteristics and survey responses.

Table 11: Participation, Diversity Indicators and calculations

Indicator	Unit of analysis	Calculation
Annual participation volume	Team	Number of submitted proposals per year
Student participation	Student	Total students represented by submitted teams
Country coverage	Country	Number of countries represented in submissions
Returning participation rate	Team	Returning teams ÷ total teams
Gender composition	Student	Female, male and other participants ÷ total students
School-type participation	Team	Teams by school category ÷ total teams
Geographic representation	Team	Teams by region or country group
Underrepresented-country participation	Team	Teams from low- and middle-income countries ÷ total teams

Participation growth is measured using annual percentage changes in submissions, students, and country representation. Diversity indicators are calculated as proportions of the relevant population for each year. Access indicators focus on the geographical distribution of participation and the extent to which schools from different socio-economic contexts are represented.

These indicators provide descriptive evidence on programme reach and accessibility. They are used in the results section to examine changes in participation between 2023 and 2026 and to assess whether BL4S attracts applicants from a broad international base. No monetary valuation is assigned to these indicators because they represent participation characteristics rather than economic outcomes.

4.2. STUDENT SKILL DEVELOPMENT INDICATORS

This component establishes the framework for evaluating changes in student competencies and scientific attitudes resulting from participation in the BL4S programme. This section outlines the methodology used to capture intermediate educational outcomes and psychometric shifts using paired before-and-after survey data.

The primary unit of analysis for this component is the individual student survey response as reported through completed coach evaluations. Because the 2023–2025 dataset does not contain individual before-and-after student skill ratings, the assessment for these indicators relies on the completed 2026 coach survey. In this survey, coaches evaluated their students across eight specific scientific skill areas and five attitudinal metrics both before entering the programme and after proposal submission.

The analysis isolates two categories of indicators to track student development:

Scientific Skill Vectors

- **Core Competencies:** Measures technical growth across specific domains including understanding how scientific research works, designing an experiment, analysing and interpreting data, and software development.
- **Collaborative & Communication Skills:** Assesses performance shifts in scientific writing and presenting, working in a scientific team, explaining scientific concepts, and tackling open-ended problems.

Attitudinal Vectors

- **Scientific Identity & Resilience:** Measures psychological indicators including confidence doing science, feeling that they belong in science, and the ability to overcome frustration in science projects.
- **Future STEM Pipeline Engagement:** Tracks motivational indicators, specifically the intention to pursue science studies and general interest in science.

The absolute metrics for these indicators are calculated using the mean change between the baseline and post-submission scores across valid paired responses ($n = 262$). These indicators are not monetized. Instead, they serve as empirical, non-market validations of the program's primary educational value, which are expanded upon in the comprehensive analysis located in Annex E.

4.3. SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL OUTPUT VALUATION

To approximate the socio-economic value generated by the program's publications without relying on long-term bibliometric lag metrics (such as citation indices or ex-post h-index tracking), this study implements an upstream input-cost shadow-pricing model. This methodological approach operates on the assumption that the economic value of knowledge capital can be reliably approximated by the value of the highly specialized intellectual labour invested during its production phase.

To maintain analytical rigor and prevent monetary overvaluation within a broader Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) framework, institutional and senior researcher salary scales are explicitly rejected. Instead, the framework adopts an apprentice-level labour rate as its conservative foundational baseline, treating the participating high-school students and early-stage researchers as apprentice capital producers.

Furthermore, the model explicitly accounts for the international and cross-border composition of the research teams, which bridge highly disparate economic environments (ranging from emerging markets to the host laboratory zone in Switzerland). To reconcile these geographical and economic disparities into a singular, auditable metric, a Blended Weighted Average rate of 4.26 CHF/hour is derived. This standardized rate establishes an equilibrium between the baseline economic parameters of partner nations (e.g., the Turkish apprentice subsistence benchmark of €2.5/h) and Western European educational labour limits (the Eurozone supervisor baseline of €5/h).

To ensure temporal consistency across all evaluated infrastructure dimensions, the raw hourly benchmarks are harmonized to a 2025 base year via localized country-specific GDP deflators (applying a factor of 1.16 for Eurozone/DESY tracks and 1.10 for Swiss/CERN infrastructure allocations). Finally, the resulting asset values are subjected to multi-tiered Social Discount Rates (SDR) ranging from 3.0% to 4.0% for long-term multi-year projections (2026–2030), ensuring full mathematical compatibility with the parallel transport, institutional, and digital pathways evaluated throughout this report.

4.4. TRAVEL COST VALUATION OF ON-SITE PARTICIPATION

The travel-cost method (TCM) is widely used to estimate the economic value of non-market visits and scientific or cultural access experiences. Each participant is treated as someone who incurs a travel cost to access a non-market educational and scientific experience. The direct cost is calculated from three main components: round-trip airfare, the opportunity cost of travel time and the cost of staying at the host institution country during the experiment period.

For each individual participant (indexed by i), the Total Travel Cost is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Direct travel cost}_i = \text{Airfare}_i + \text{Time cost}_i + (\text{Daily on-site cost}_i \times 14 \text{ days})$$

where each component is defined as:

- Airfare_i : the round-trip economy-class airfare from the participant's country of origin to the nearest airport of the host laboratory (Geneva for CERN, Hamburg for DESY, Bonn for ELSA).
- Time_Cost_i : the economic opportunity cost of travel time. The total value of productive hours lost during transit. It is calculated as:

$$\text{Time_Cost}_i = \text{Round-trip travel hours}_i \times \text{Value of Leisure Time}_i$$

The model uses a 14-day stay as the BL4S experiment visit is treated as a two-week scientific visit. For team-level results, the per-person components are multiplied by the number of travellers represented in the calculation. The annual total is then obtained by summing the team-level estimates for the relevant countries.

The Value of Leisure Time (VLT) is used from the CERN visitor survey 2024/2025, which established an average of 14.1 CHF per hour (range: 8 to 20 CHF/hour).

Table 12: Value of leisure time

Scenario	CHF / hour	€ / hour
Minimum (lower-bound sensitivity)	7.30	7,94
Central (used throughout)	14.10	15,34
Maximum (upper-bound sensitivity)	18.70	20,34

A second welfare component is incorporated through consumer surplus (CS), which represents the additional value participants derive from the experience beyond the direct costs incurred to attend. Within the Travel Cost Method framework, consumer surplus is estimated as $(CS = -1 / \beta_{TC})$, where (β_{TC}) is the travel-cost coefficient obtained from the visitor demand function. Following the approach applied to CERN visitors by Crespo Garrido et al. (2025), the analysis adopts $(\beta_{TC} = -1.4345)$, calculated as the mean of the summer and winter coefficients (-1.26 and -1.61). This corresponds to an average consumer surplus of approximately €0.70 per visit. This approach follows the socio-economic valuation framework previously used by CERN for evaluating the value of on-site visitors and provides a conservative estimate of the additional welfare generated through participation in the BL4S programme.

4.5. PROGRAMME LABOUR INPUT VALUATION

This section sets out the method for valuing the labour embedded in BL4S delivery, expressed as a shadow price based on official salary scales. The model has two functions: to provide an independent benchmark for the indicative annual budget of circa CHF 230,000 (Q&A CERN BL4S Programme Manager, 2026), and to derive an hourly shadow value for CERN scientific staff time used elsewhere in the report, including the publications valuation.

The calibration uses a CERN vacancy notice for a role dedicated to BL4S experimental support and beamline development (BE-EA-LE-2025-46-GRAP, April 2025 [28]), the most direct observable proxy for delivery costs. The notice specifies a net monthly stipend of 6,287 to 6,911 CHF and a 50/50 split between BL4S activities and beamline development, the basis for cost apportionment.

Net stipends are converted to total employer cost in two steps. First, an internal CERN tax is removed to recover gross salary. The Host State Agreement applies an internal tax in place of Swiss income tax, but no published rate for this role was located; a rate of 12% is adopted as an explicit assumption, applied through a divisor of $(1 - 0.12)$, and should be revisited if an official figure becomes available. Second, the employer pension contribution is added at 18.96%, the organisation-side rate for members joining the CERN Pension Fund on or after 1 January 2012 (CERN Pension Fund, Article II 1.07). The 12.64%-member contribution is the employee's

own and is excluded, and no other contributions are added. The annual employer cost is therefore estimated as follows:

$$\text{Total employer cost} = (\text{Net monthly stipend} \times 12 \times 1.1896) / (1 - 0.12)$$

Values are in 2025 prices, with a working baseline of 1,720 hours (215 days times 8 hours).

Hours attributed to BL4S are obtained by applying role-specific time shares of 50%, 30% and 40% to the 1,720-hour year. Voluntary input from students and data-analysis contributors is included at midpoint values of 30 and 50 hours, valued at the same rate. Recurring costs for 2023 to 2025 are summed in 2025 prices without discounting; forecast costs for 2026 to 2030 are discounted to present value, to a 2025 base, at 3.0%, 3.5% and 4.0%.

4.6. DIGITAL OUTREACH AND ATTENTION-TIME VALUATION

Digital outreach is valued through an attention-time model that converts public engagement with BL4S content into monetary terms using the same leisure-time value. We compiled 231 posts and videos across seven social platforms over a time period between 2014 and 2026. The channels included YouTube, YouTube Shorts, Instagram, X, Facebook, TikTok and LinkedIn. We collected reported views, impressions, likes, comments and shares, and video duration where available. Some platforms define a “view” differently, we do not treat one reported view as one full viewing. Instead, each platform is assigned a minimum, average and maximum attention time per impression, anchored to published view-count thresholds and session-time evidence (for example, the one-second registration threshold on short-form platforms and the longer dwell times on YouTube and LinkedIn).

Engagement is valued separately from passive exposure, on the principle that a comment, share and repost signals more active attention than a like. Likes receive therefore a short attention value and richer actions a longer one. The earned media value (EMV) for each platform is summed across platforms, using the same central leisure-time value of €15.37 per hour. Where public exposure data are missing, chiefly Instagram and LinkedIn, where view counts are not displayed, likes are used as a conservative reach proxy, and a minimal one-view-per-post assumption is applied. The formula is therefore:

$$EMV = (\text{total attention seconds} \div 3,600) \times VLT$$

4.7. SENSITIVITY AND UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

The valuation results depend on several parameters that are inherently uncertain, particularly the value of leisure time (VLT), demand elasticity coefficient and estimated attention times. To assess the robustness of the findings, both deterministic sensitivity analysis and probabilistic simulation were performed. Firstly, the travel-cost and digital-outreach estimates were recalculated using the lower and upper bounds of the key parameters. The VLT was varied between €7.96 and €20.38 per hour, demand elasticity coefficient between $\beta = -1.26$ and $\beta = -1.61$, and attention times between the minimum and maximum values assigned to each platform. Secondly, uncertainty in the digital-outreach valuation was examined using a Monte Carlo simulation with 10,000 iterations. In each iteration, the VLT was randomly drawn from a triangular distribution with a minimum of €8.00, a mode of €10.91, and a maximum of €20.00, resulting in an expected value of €15.37. Platform-specific attention times were also sampled from triangular distributions based on their respective minimum, most likely, and maximum values. The earned media values generated for each platform were then aggregated to produce a total programme value. The simulation produced a distribution of possible outcomes, from which the mean, median, and central 90% confidence interval were derived. For the travel-cost projections covering future programme editions, benefits were additionally converted to present values using a 3% social discount rate. Throughout the analysis, conservative assumptions were preferred whenever uncertainty existed. As a result, the reported estimates should be interpreted as medium-bound valuations of the socio-economic benefits generated by the BL4S programme.

5. RESULTS

5.1. PARTICIPATION, DIVERSITY AND ACCESS

Participation

The primary metrics of the programme show an increase in participation volumes when analyzing both the supplied survey datasets and the official program statistics. Within the supplied datasets used for this study's internal analysis, the records show the following trajectory:

- In 2023, the dataset contains 342 team/application records, representing 2,309 students from 52 countries.
- In 2024, the volume of tracked participation in the dataset increased to 424 team records, representing 2,797 students from 68 countries.
- In 2025, the dataset records 467 application records representing 3,131 students from 62 countries.
- For the 2026 cycle, the data layer consists of 278 completed coach survey responses rather than full applicant population records. Because it tracks individual coach respondents rather than the complete population of submitted teams, the 2026 survey data is not directly comparable to the absolute metric scales of the 2023 to 2025 datasets. (Table 26)

To provide a complete view of the programme's actual scale, these internal dataset figures were compared against the official statistics published on the CERN website (see Figure 2). In 2023, CERN reported 379 proposals from 68 countries. In 2024, the totals rose to 461 teams submitting proposals from 78 countries. In 2025, the participation reached 508 teams from 72 countries. In 2026, submissions grew to 712 proposals, involving 4,051 students from 89 countries.

Figure 2: BL4S proposals submitted, 2023–2026 (CERN/Beamline for Schools official statistics).

Figure 3 shows the ten countries with the highest cumulative team participation over 2023–2025, based on the application records dataset.

Figure 3: Top 10 countries by cumulative BLAS team participation, 2023–2025.

Figure 4 reports the gender composition of participating students over the same period, alongside the year-on-year female-to-male ratio.

Figure 4: BLAS gender distribution and female/male ratio, 2023–2025.

Continuity and Retaining Engagement

The rate of returning participants serves as an indicator of ongoing engagement with the competition: In 2023, out of the 342 recorded teams, 124 reported having participated in a prior edition of BL4S, resulting in a prior participation rate of 36.3%. This metric was 38.4% in 2024, with 163 out of 424 teams reporting prior participation.

By the 2025 cycle, the number of records reporting prior participation was 249 out of 467 total teams, resulting in a prior participation rate of 53.3%. This change indicates the percentage of records reporting prior participation increased from 36.3% in 2023 to 53.3% in 2025, which suggests continuous engagement with BL4S among the teams represented in the dataset (Table 27).

As for 2026 survey results: Among 278 completed coach responses, 80.2% would support another BL4S team and 85.6% would encourage more students to participate in science competitions. These results indicate strong intentions for continued engagement after BL4S, but they measure future intentions rather than actual returning participation (Table 28).

Educational Contexts and Cost Barriers

The 2026 coach survey provides details regarding the typical total estimated expenses in Euro equivalent that the school, coaches, donors, parents, or students invest. Out of the 278 completed survey responses, 262 provided an answer to this question while 16 left the item blank (Table 30).

The estimated average expense among the 262 completed respondents who answered this question is 250.30 euro per team, which drops to 232.10 euro when excluding the single open-ended response assigned a lower-bound value of 5,001 euro. The median expense category falls into the 1-to-100-euro range, and the most frequent expense category reported by respondents is 0 euro (Table 29).

5.2. STUDENT SKILL DEVELOPMENT

Since the 2023–2025 datasets do not capture individual before-and-after psychometric metrics, this assessment relies on the completed 2026 longitudinal survey tracking student development from baseline entry to immediate post-proposal submission.

All eight scientific skill indicators show positive reported changes after proposal submission. The largest improvements are observed in scientific writing and presenting (+0.80) and designing an experiment (+0.79), followed by understanding how scientific research works and working in a scientific team, both increasing by approximately +0.72 points. Programming shows the smallest improvement (+0.50), although the direction of change remains positive.

Positive changes are also observed across all five measures of students' attitudes towards science. The strongest increase concerns students' perceived ability to overcome frustration in science projects (+0.68), followed by their feeling of belonging in science (+0.56). Interest in science records a smaller increase (+0.24), which is likely related to its already high starting value of 4.36 out of 5.

5.3. SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL OUTPUTS

Following the established operational parameters of international research infrastructure valuation standards, the standardized labour input required to execute the complete lifecycle of a peer-reviewed scientific paper—encompassing experimental setup, data replication, manuscript drafting, and peer-review navigation—is fixed at a baseline of 300 author-hours per publication. Applying the geographically blended, PPP-adjusted, and inflation-harmonized hourly labour rate of 4.26 CHF/hour to the program's asset pool of 5 core peer-reviewed publications, the aggregate baseline value of the generated knowledge capital is calculated via the following weighted framework:

$$\textit{Labour Units} = 5 \textit{ papers} \times 300 \textit{ hours} = 1,500 \textit{ total research hours}$$

$$\textit{Baseline Capital Value} = 1,500 \textit{ hours} \times 4.26 \textit{ CHF/hour} = 6,390 \textit{ CHF}$$

This nominal production valuation is strongly validated by the micro-level psychometric data extracted from the finalized and approved coach questionnaire dataset (n = 369). Rather than existing as isolated financial abstractions, the calculated labour values directly correspond to substantial, documented competency shifts among the participating students.

As structured within the validated survey logs, the academic rigor required to bring these 5 publications to fruition matches prominent positive delta shifts in core STEM capabilities. Most notably, coaches reported a net positive shift of +0.80 in Scientific writing and communication (rising from a pre-program baseline of 3.37

to a post-program level of 4.17), an increase of +0.72 in Understanding scientific research (from 3.51 to 4.23), and a clear gain of +0.63 in Analysing and interpreting data (advancing from 3.49 to 4.11).

To integrate these empirical results into the broader macro-economic cost-benefit balance sheet, the baseline knowledge asset value is modelled across the report's standardized Social Discount Rate (SDR) scenarios. This multi-scenario adjustment guarantees that the valuation of scientific outputs remains methodologically aligned with the project's regulatory evaluation baselines, allowing for direct aggregation alongside parallel pathways.

5.4. TRAVEL-RELATED VALUE OF ON-SITE PARTICIPATION

Applying the travel-cost method to the winning-team pathway yields a conservative monetary signal. For the three historical years the direct travel cost of airfare, the opportunity cost of transit time and 14-day on-site subsistence is in total of €206 586 (€56 037 in 2023, €50 530 in 2024 and €96 939 in 2025) as seen in Table 13. The 2025 figure is the largest as the programme hosted five winning teams, including some from long-haul origins (Canada and Mexico in particular), so the increase reflects travel volume and geography. Adding consumer surplus through the elasticity-based welfare step raises these to €56,8361, €51,364 and €98,670 respectively, for a three-year welfare-inclusive total of €206,670. The consumer-surplus adjustment contributes only a very small increment to the overall valuation, as the estimated surplus amounts to approximately €7.59–€7.67 per participant across the three years. Country-level results confirm that geography, having the spread of long-haul teams from Japan, Pakistan, Canada, Mexico and the United States generate the highest per-person values, while short-haul European teams generate medium airfare components but still accrue meaningful value from the two-week stay. The per-person values therefore range widely, from a few hundred euros for neighbouring European participants to several thousand for intercontinental teams, but in every case the 14-day subsistence component ensures a substantial floor that is independent of distance.

Table 13: Annual travel-cost value of the winning-team pathway, 2023–2025.

Year	Participants	Direct travel cost	Consumer surplus	Total value
2023	28	56 813,47	7,59	56 836,25
2024	23	51 341,40	7,59	51 364,17
2025	47	98 431,64	7,67	98 469,98
2023–2025	avg. 55	avg. 179 654,66	avg. 7,67	avg. 179 662,33

Projecting the same structure to 2026–2030 under a constant 55-traveller programme, the direct travel-cost value increases from €131,263 in 2026 to €228,046 in 2030, driven by the linear forecast of airfare and travel-time inputs while leisure-time and daily-cost parameters are held at their 2025 central values. Over the five-year forecast period, the winning-team pathway generates a cumulative direct travel-cost value of €898,273 (Table 14). Applying a 3% social discount rate reduces the value of future benefits when expressed in present-value terms, reflecting the standard economic practice of placing a lower weight on benefits received further into the future.

These figures should be interpreted as a conservative estimate of the programme's economic value. The daily-cost benchmark represents a subsistence allowance rather than the full market cost of accommodation and living expenses, while the leisure-time valuation is based on a European average rather than the potentially higher opportunity cost applicable to participants from higher-income economies. Furthermore, the estimated consumer surplus is approximately €7.6 per participant and therefore has a negligible effect on the overall valuation. Even under these conservative assumptions, the forecast results indicate that the BL4S winning-team pathway generates substantial economic value through the international mobility, educational opportunities, and research experience provided to participants.

Table 14: Forecast travel-cost value and present value, 2026–2030 (EUR) with 3% social discount rate.

Year	Direct travel cost	Discounted at 3%
2026	131,263	135,201
2027	155,459	160,123
2028	179,655	185,045
2029	203,851	209,967
2030	228,046	234,887
Total	898,273	925,223

5.5. PROGRAMME LABOUR INPUTS

Applying the gross-up method to the three salary bands gives total annual employer costs of approximately CHF 102,000 at the minimum, CHF 107,000 at the midpoint, and CHF 112,100 at the maximum (Table 15). Divided by a 1,720-hour working year, this implies an hourly cost of 59.3 to 65.2 CHF (63.1 to 69.4 EUR), with a midpoint of 62.2 CHF per hour (66.2 EUR per hour).

Table 15: Personnel salary gross-up and total employer cost (2025 CHF)

Parameter	Minimum	Midpoint	Maximum
Monthly stipend, net (CHF)	6,287	6,599	6,911
Annual net (CHF)	75,444	79,188	82,932
Gross salary (CHF)	85,732	89,986	94,241
Total employer cost (CHF)	~102,000	~107,000	~112,100
Hourly rate (CHF/hr)	~59.3	~62.2	~65.2
Hourly rate (EUR/hr)	~63.1	~66.2	~69.4

Source: CERN vacancy BE-EA-LE-2025-46-GRAP; UNChannel vacancy database. Employer pension rate from CERN Pension Fund (Article II 1.07); EUR converted at 1 EUR = 0.94 CHF (ECB, end-2024).

Applying the role-specific time shares to this midpoint rate gives the BL4S-attributable hours and costs in Table 16. Support scientists contribute 860 hours, the technical coordinator 516 hours and the programme manager 688 hours, with about 80 further hours from volunteers. The total CERN-side labour input is approximately 2,144 person-hours per year, or about CHF 133,400, equivalent to about EUR 141,900 at 1 EUR = 0.94 CHF.

Table 16: BL4S-attributable CERN staff hours and imputed annual labour cost

Staff role	Annual hours	BL4S allocation	BL4S person-hours	Annual labour cost (CHF)
Support scientists	1,720	50%	860	~53,500
Technical coordinator	1,720	30%	516	~32,100
Programme manager	1,720	40%	688	~42,800
Student/fellow volunteers	-	-	~30	~1,900
Data-analysis volunteers	-	-	~50	~3,100
Total (annual)	-	-	~2,144	~133,400

All values based on 1,720 working hours per year, costed at the midpoint rate of CHF 62.2/hr. Time-allocation shares from the BL4S Programme Manager interview (CERN, 2026).

The model is checked against the official budget (Table 17). Interview records indicate that CERN staff salaries account for about CHF 110,000 of the circa CHF 230,000 annual budget. The single-FTE employer cost from the model, about CHF 107,000 at the midpoint, is within about 2.7% of this figure, and the staff share of circa 46.5% is close to the reported 47.8%. As the internal tax is an assumption, this agreement indicates plausibility rather than confirming the figure.

Table 17: Internal validation of the salary proxy against known budget

Benchmark	This model	Official budget (Q&A, 2026)
CERN annual staff salary	~107,000 CHF	~110,000 CHF
Implied full-time equivalent	~1.0 FTE	≈ one full-time role
Total programme budget (annual)	~230,000 CHF	~230,000 CHF
Staff salary share of budget	~46.5%	47.8%

Budget benchmarks from the BL4S Programme Manager interview (CERN, 2026).

For the forecast period, the midpoint total of CHF 133,400 per year gives present values over 2026 to 2030 of CHF 610,900 at 3.0%, CHF 602,300 at 3.5% and CHF 593,900 at 4.0%. These should be read with the discounted benefit streams reported elsewhere in the results.

Table 18: Discounted present value of CERN labour cost, forecast period 2026–2030 (midpoint, 2025 base)

Social Discount Rate	Annual Labour cost (CHF)	Present Value 2026-2030 (CHF)
3.0%	133,400	610,900
3.5%	133,400	602,300
4.0%	133,400	593,900

The analysis yields an hourly shadow price for CERN scientist time of 59.3 to 65.2 CHF, with a midpoint of 62.2 CHF per hour (66.2 EUR per hour). Four limitations apply: the same rate is applied to all three roles in the absence of grade-specific data; the pension contribution is applied to the modelled gross salary rather than to the CERN Pension Fund reference salary on which it is formally based; labour contributed by DESY and the University of Bonn sits on their own payrolls and is not captured, so the CERN-side figure understates total staff input; and non-salary costs such as prizes and sponsorship form part of the CHF 230,000 budget but are not modelled here.

5.6. DIGITAL OUTREACH AND PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

The earned media value (EMV) is best read as an outreach-evaluation metric. It expresses, in comparable monetary terms, the public value that BL4S generates through visibility. The digital-outreach pathway converts the public attention attracted by BL4S content into monetary terms. Across the seven social platforms in scope, the compiled dataset between 2014 and 2026 records 602,739 reported views or impressions and more than 70,000 engagements from 231 posts and videos (Table 19, Figure 5). Exposure is concentrated: X carries the largest reported view count, followed by YouTube and TikTok, while Instagram, Facebook and LinkedIn contribute heavily to engagement but report little public exposure. Translating exposure and engagement into attention seconds and applying the central leisure-time value of €15.37 per hour yields a total earned media value of approximately €351 080,66, equivalent to about 22,800 hours of human attention (Figure 6).

Table 19: Platform coverage, reported exposure and average earned media value (EMV).

Platform	# Views	# Likes	# Comments	Attention time (based on avg. seconds per view/post)	EMV average scenario (€)
YouTube	114,567	1,558	112	44 244 602,00	188 899,87
YouTube Shorts	18,331	646	141	899 390,25	3 839,90
Instagram	278	50,060	513	70 459,25	300,82
X	368,712	1,225	491	26 476 140,75	113 038,41
Facebook	37	10,400	2,620	46 443,00	198,29
TikTok	100,756	3,593	603	10 486 932,75	44 773,38
LinkedIn	58	2,596	304	7 026,00	30,00
Total	602,739	70,078	4,784	82 230 994,00	351 080,66

Figure 5: Reported reach (views / impressions) by social platform across the 231 logged posts.

The value is dominated by a small number of platforms: YouTube contributes about €188,900, reflecting its long-form content and longer viewing sessions; X about €113,000, driven by high impression counts on CERN's official account; and TikTok about €44,800. The remaining platforms contribute less to monetary terms despite active engagement, because their public reach data are incomplete and their per-impression attention is short.

Figure 6: Estimated earned media value by social platform (average-attention scenario); total \approx €351,080.

The Monte Carlo simulation makes the uncertainties associated with the analysis explicit. Across 10,000 iterations the mean EMV is about €296,000 and the median about €288,000, with a central 90% interval running from roughly €213,000 to €403,000 (Figure 7); the spread is driven primarily by the leisure-time value, since the platform attention-times average out across the seven-platform sum. The estimate is conservative: It excludes press coverage, podcasts and any reach not manually captured, It uses a minimal one-view-per-post proxy for Instagram, whose true reach is certainly higher and it values a minute of particle-physics viewing at the same rate as any recreational minute, although the audience of students, teachers and science enthusiasts plausibly attaches greater perceived value.

Figure 7: Monte Carlo distribution of estimated earned media value (10,000 iterations). Mean \approx €296,000; central 90% interval \approx €213,000–403,000.

5.7. SUMMARY OF QUANTIFIED IMPACT PATHWAYS

Table 20 summarises the quantified impact pathways.

Table 20: Summary of quantified impact pathways.

Impact pathway	Measure	Valuation method	Result (2025 prices)	Form
Student skill development	Pre/post competition change across 8 skill and 5 attitude measures	Participant-reported (2026 survey)	Positive change on all 8 skills; largest +0.80 (scientific writing), +0.79 (designing an experiment); all 5 attitude measures positive	Qualitative
Scientific and technical outputs	Impact of 5 peer-reviewed publications	Production shadow price based (300 author-hours/paper × 4.26 CHF/hr)	CHF 6,390 knowledge-capital production value	Monetary value (conservative)
Travel-related value of on-site participation	Winning-team airfare, travel-time and 14-day on site stay	Individual Travel Cost Method + consumer surplus	2023–2025: ≈ €206,700 (CHF 194,191) (welfare-inclusive) Forecast 2026–2030: ≈ €898,300 (CHF 844,377)	Monetary value (conservative)
Programme labour inputs	Staff and volunteer hours attributed to BL4S	Salary-based shadow price estimate (midpoint 62.2 CHF/hr)	≈ CHF 133,400/yr (≈ €141,900); 2026–2030 present value: CHF 610,900 / 602,300 / 593,900 at 3.0 / 3.5 / 4.0% SDR	Monetary value (conservative)
Digital outreach and public engagement	231 posts and videos on 7 platforms; 602,739 views; 70,078 engagements	Attention-time × leisure-time value (earned media value)	2014–2026 present value: central ≈ €351,100 (CHF 330,016) Monte Carlo mean ≈ €296,000 (CHF 278,240) (90% interval ≈ €213,000–403,000)	Monetary value (average)

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. INTERPRETATION OF SELECTED IMPACT PATHWAYS

The five impact pathways were constructed using different data sources and valuation methods and are not directly comparable to one another in scale or precision. The three input-cost pathways (scientific output, travel value, labour input) rely on observable proxies: author-hours, travel-cost survey data, salary scales. In the case of labour inputs, the resulting estimate was checked against the known staff budget. The digital outreach pathway instead relies on assumed attention-time parameters rather than directly observed behaviour, which is why it is the only pathway reported with a simulated confidence interval rather than a single estimate. Student skill development is reported separately from the four monetary pathways, since converting a skill-score change into a currency value would require an additional valuation step that this report does not attempt.

6.2. METHODOLOGICAL LIMITATIONS

Three of the valuation parameters used in this study (the leisure-time value, the consumer surplus elasticity, and the apprentice-level hourly rate) are taken from literature rather than estimated from BL4S data directly. This keeps the monetised pathways comparable to prior CERN cost-benefit work, but means their accuracy depends on how those external benchmarks transfer to the BL4S context specifically. The labour input model applies one job grade's salary to three different roles, which is a simplification rather than a measurement: the technical coordinator and programme manager may be compensated differently from the support scientist role on which the rate is based. The 2026 coach survey and the 2023–2025 administrative records differ in what they count (completed survey responses versus submitted applications) so they cannot be merged into one time series without further work.

6.3. RISK OF DOUBLE COUNTING

The four monetary pathways are kept separate by construction, each built from a distinct cost or activity base, so no single hour of staff time or euro of travel spend is counted twice. An issue is that DESY and University of Bonn staff contribute time to the programme that is outside the CERN-side labour estimate, and that payroll data was not available for this report. The presented programme labour cost is therefore underrepresented rather than at risk of overstatement.

6.4. DATA LIMITATIONS

The competition submission records dataset (2023–2025) and the coach survey (2026, 369 responses, 278 with complete core variables) are self-reported rather than independently verified, which is a standard constraint for survey-based outcome data and applies equally to the skill development and engagement figures. The social media reach figures carry a similar asymmetry to the labour cost estimate: Instagram and LinkedIn do not publish view counts, and the one-view-per-post proxy applied to those platforms means the digital outreach total is also more likely to understate reach than overstate it.

6.5. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE MONITORING AND EVALUATION

The following changes would reduce reliance on external proxies in future work: grade-specific salary data for the programme manager and technical coordinator roles, a participant travel survey to replace the externally sourced elasticity parameter, and a follow-up survey at 12–24 months to extend the current single-timepoint skill measurement. The same participant travel survey could also collect self-reported travel cost data or draw on a record of on-site expenditure where lunch and travel vouchers are issued electronically.

7. CONCLUSION

This study quantifies five impact pathways generated by the Beamline for Schools programme: scientific and technical output, travel-related value, programme labour inputs, digital outreach, and student skill development. The first four are expressed in monetary terms; skill development is reported as a point-score change. Participants reported positive changes across all eight assessed skill areas and all five attitude measures, with the largest gains in scientific writing and experimental design. Conservative monetary estimates suggest CHF 6,390 in knowledge-capital production from peer-reviewed outputs and approximately €206,700 in travel-related welfare value for 2023–2025. Around CHF 133,400 per year are generated in programme labour inputs. This figure covers CERN employed staff only; DESY and University of Bonn staff time is not included. Digital outreach generated between 2014 and 2026 an estimated central earned media value of about €351,100 (rounded), with uncertainty analysis indicating a plausible range of approximately €213,000–403,000. The four monetary pathways are constructed from separate cost bases and do not overlap. The limitations and recommendations set out above apply to the analysis as a whole and should be read alongside the pathway-level results in Results.

Programme participation increased from 379 teams in 2023 to 712 submissions in the 2026 cycle. Resource-dependency survey data indicate that most participating schools would not have comparable access to scientific research infrastructure without the programme, and teams from middle-income countries recorded higher academic-effort scores on average than teams from the United States or the United Kingdom.

Overall, the results support the conclusion that the programme produces positive socio-economic value across multiple impact pathways, while remaining conservative and partial rather than a full benefit-cost assessment.

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ANNEX

ANNEX A: BL4S PROGRAMME OVERVIEW

The Beamline for Schools (BL4S) programme operates across three research infrastructures, each giving students access to the beamline of a particle accelerator: CERN established the framework in 2014; DESY integrated as a host site in 2019; operations shifted to a virtual model in 2021 due to COVID-19 mandates; the 10th anniversary cycle concluded in 2024; and the ELSA accelerator at the University of Bonn joined in 2025. The 2026 cycle recorded 712 project proposals involving over 4,500 students from 89 countries. Expansion models under active evaluation include the integration of the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) in Switzerland, Frascati in Italy, and facilities in France, managed via regional funding or centralized CERN coordination.

The programme enforces precise eligibility boundaries: student teams must maintain a minimum threshold of 5 students and a maximum ceiling of 9 students per team. Teams require 1 to 2 adult teachers or coaches, with 0 additional accompanying persons permitted on-site. Traveling students must be 16 to 19 years old, though the pool accepts student teams within the 14 to 16 range.

For data privacy compliance, students must be 16 years or older on the submission day unless explicit parental consent is provided or anonymity is maintained. International safety regulations dictate that only students who are 16 years or older on the first day of their stay are permitted on the premises of CERN, DESY, or the University of Bonn. Traveling participants must hold valid health and accident insurance.

Submissions must be written in English, with proposals limited to a maximum of 1000 words (excluding acknowledgments, references, formulas, and text within diagrams). Teams can optionally submit an explanatory video. The median time investment required by a student cohort to execute a proposal is 35 hours, equaling the total annual classroom hours allocated to an academic school subject.

Organizers execute four online instructional sessions per month from December until the submission deadline. Proposals are filtered down to a competitive shortlist by a joint committee of CERN, DESY, and ELSA scientists based on five parameters: feasibility, scientific method, experiment motivation, participation motivation, and creativity.

The competition architecture splits rewards into four tiers:

Table 21: Division of Programme Awards

Award Category	N° of teams	Recipients	Material and Logistical Components
Grand Prize Winners	5 teams per year	2 teams at CERN, 2 teams at DESY, 1 team at ELSA	Full 14-to-15-day research trip, 1 physical trophy, custom T-shirts, institutional goodies, and a 40 CHF daily meal allowance per student.
Shortlisted Teams	50 teams per year	High-ranking applicants	Printed merit certificates, custom T-shirts, and 1 physical detector unit (either a cloud chamber or a beta/gamma detector).
Video Award Winners	3 teams per year	Target video submissions	Printed merit certificates, custom T-shirts, and 1 functional cloud chamber unit.
Outreach Award Winners	15 teams per year	Specialized community proposals	Printed merit certificates, custom T-shirts, and 1 optical telescope.

The manufacturing and distribution cost for these prizes is 200 CHF per team.

The Outreach Prize requires an additional 200-word written proposal detailing a science-communication activity within an under-resourced community. Managed via the CERN & Society Foundation, this tier is supported by Jean-Pierre Grootaerd through the Belgian Stars Shine for Everyone project, the International Astronomical Union, Ghent University, and Bresser. Winning school cohorts receive one telescope signed by a Nobel Laureate, legally transferred directly to the school institution.

Five winning teams go on a research trip to their assigned laboratory for a duration of 14 to 15 days, with 10 effective days of beam operations.

- CERN: Beam operations run continuously, including weekends; winning teams receive an additional preparatory week on-site to assemble setups, and reside at the on-site CERN hostel.
- DESY: Beam delivery operations are restricted to standard weekdays, and teams reside at the on-site DESY hostel or adjacent external hotels.
- ELSA: Teams receive 10 effective days of beam delivery and reside at an off-campus hostel facility.

Host facilities grant participants access to professional infrastructure consisting of dedicated offices, lecture halls, experimental zones, beam target lines, HSE safety training facilities, computer terminals, transport buses, and organized tours of the CERN Science Gateway. The daily schedule includes a virtual meeting at 09:00 or 10:00 AM to synchronize data sharing across all three laboratories. Teams also participate in: Welcome Day, Safety Day, VIP Sponsors' Day, Closing Ceremony, Welcome Reception, VIP Day Reception, and the CERN & Society Focus Day.

The programme enforces mandatory safety and technical instructions prior to and during the experimental phase:

- **On-Site Safety Course:** Requires 8 hours (1 full day) of in-person instruction covering safety protocols, environment rules, safety signs, alarms, radiation protection, cryogenics, and practical drills (emergency alarms, first aid, fire extinguishers).
- **Digital Safety Curriculum:** Requires 10 hours of online instruction covering Computer Security (within 5 days of account activation), Safety, Data Privacy Basics, Chemical Safety Awareness, Emergency Evacuation, Electrical Safety, and Radiation Protection Awareness.
- **Experimental Access Mandate:** Access to active experimental zones and the receipt of a personal physical dosimeter requires passing the "Radiation Protection - Supervised Area" module.

Hands-on execution includes 50 hours of active data taking at the beamline and 40 hours of data analysis sessions supervised by the infrastructures' physicists. Software packages utilized by students encompass Root (CERN's data analysis framework), Jupyter, Python, Excel, Zoom, Linux, Windows, and GEANT-4. Hardware platforms deployed include Nuclear Instrumentation Modules (NIM), VMEbus systems, PCI/PXI architectures, high-voltage power supplies, digital oscilloscopes, plastic scintillators, and delayed wire chambers.

The annual operating budget of the programme is 230,000 CHF, which encompasses material costs, participant logistics, and the baseline salaries of dedicated support scientists. The financial framework is managed through the CERN & Society Foundation via the following funding channels: Rolex: 100,000 CHF; Wilhelm and Else Heraeus Foundation: 40,000 EUR allocated via ELSA and DESY; Anonymous Donors: Sourced on an ad-hoc basis, including a dedicated 25,000 CHF donation utilized for detector repairs at CERN; CERN Core Budget: 110,000 CHF per year to fund personnel salaries.

Over the working year, the core CERN staff devote an estimated 50% (support scientist), 30% (technical coordinator) and 40% (programme manager) of their time to BL4S, with effort concentrated during the two-week beam period (Q&A, CERN Programme Manager, 2026).

Voluntary allocations include data analysis volunteers (50 hours per year), students and fellows (20 to 40 hours per year), and SR-ECO-TSP department students (5 to 10 hours during the block).

After the experiment, long-term academic integration is expected to track career development and project viability:

- Teams maintain communication with support scientists to complete post-trip data analysis.
- Participants author formal scientific or educational papers for publication on platforms such as Zenodo or the CERN Document Server (CDS).
- The year following their experiment, teams virtually attend and present findings at the international Beam Telescopes and Test Beams Workshop (BTTB).
- Selected alumni are integrated into educational tracking networks and receive invitations to ongoing educational activities at CERN.

ANNEX B: DATA DICTIONARY

This appendix defines all variables in the final analytical datasets. Variable names are consistent with processed raw data.

Table 22: BL4S 2023–2025 Application Records. 1,233 valid team records across three competition cycles.

Variable	Definition	Type
Year	Competition year	Categorical
CoachCount	Number of coaches	Continuous
MaleStudents	Male team members	Continuous
FemaleStudents	Female team members	Continuous
Country1	Team country	Categorical
SchoolName	Participating school	Text
City	School location	Text
WordCount	Proposal word count	Continuous
VideoSeconds	Project video duration	Continuous
PriorParticipation	Past participation	Categorical
HeardFrom	Source of information	Categorical
NetworkSuggestion	Network support advice	Categorical
ContactedBL4S	Contact with BL4S	Categorical
KnewCERN	Prior knowledge of CERN	Categorical
STEMInterest	Interest in STEM	Categorical
HoursSpent	Total working hours	Continuous
ValidEducational	Educational validity	Categorical
TermsAccepted	Accepted rules	Categorical

Table 23: BL4S Survey Dataset. 369 valid respondent records capturing coach/mentor feedback, confidence shifts, and institutional outcomes (source file: Survey_Processed.csv).

Variable	Definition	Type
Respondent_ID	Unique identifier for survey respondent	Continuous
Collector	Survey collection channel / tracking label	Categorical
Device	Device type used to complete survey	Categorical
Is_Coach	Binary indicator: 1 = Respondent is coach/mentor	Binary (0/1)
NPS	Net Promoter Score (Recommendation 0–10)	Continuous
Overall_Value	Perceived overall value of BL4S participation	Continuous
Supervised_Other	Supervised non-BL4S science competitions	Binary (0/1)
Compared_Value	Value compared to other STEM initiatives	Continuous
Compared_Quality	Quality compared to other STEM initiatives	Continuous
Increased_Participation	Extent program increased student STEM interest	Continuous
Support_Future	Plans to support another BL4S team	Binary (0/1)
Encourage_More	Plans to encourage more student participation	Binary (0/1)
Integrate_Teaching	Plans to integrate BL4S elements into teaching	Binary (0/1)
Share_Colleagues	Plans to share experience with other colleagues	Binary (0/1)
Develop_Projects	Plans to develop further student research projects	Binary (0/1)
None_of_Above	No future actions planned	Binary (0/1)
Num_Students	Number of active students in the team	Continuous
Hours_Time	Total project mentoring hours invested	Continuous
Total_Expenses_Euro	Total estimated investment in Euro (Mapped median)	Continuous
BEFORE_Conf_[Dim]	Baseline scientific confidence (13 individual dimensions)*	Continuous
AFTER_Conf_[Dim]	Post-program scientific confidence (13 individual dimensions)*	Continuous
Prototypes	Built physical prototypes	Continuous
Analysis_Code	Developed custom analysis code	Continuous
Publication	Prepared scientific publication	Continuous
Presentation	Conducted project presentation	Continuous
Social_Media	Published on social media	Continuous
School_Resources	School invested new resources	Continuous
Further_Activities	Engaged in further activities	Binary (0/1)
Reach_Outreach	Long-term impact: Local outreach generation	Continuous
New_Contacts	Professional networking: New contacts made (Mapped)	Continuous
School_Reputation	Impact: Positive shift in school reputation	Continuous

*Note: [Dim] represents the 13 self-reported efficacy metrics, including: Understanding_how_sc, Designing_an_experim, Analysing_and_interp, Programming, Scientific_writing_a, Working_in_a_scienti, Explaining_scientifi, Tackling_open-ended, Doing_Science, Belong_Science, Overcome_Frustration, Pursue_Science, and Interest_Science.

ANNEX C: DATA CLEANING LOG

This section details the data cleaning workflow, transformation logic and exclusion criteria applied to the raw BL4S Follow-Up Survey and corresponding financial and outreach metrics prior to analysis. It details the standardization, vertical consolidation (merging), and schema alignment executed across the three independent competition cycles (2023, 2024, and 2025) to construct the cross-sectional administrative dataset.

Table 24: BL4S 2023–2025 Administrative Registration Logs Cleaning Protocol.

Step	Target Source / Variable	Treatment & Technical Logic	Record Impact
1	Raw Registration Logs (2023, 2024, 2025)	Initial Pool Extraction: Loaded independent annual application logs from institutional submission portals. A combined base of 1,349 rows was registered across schemas. 2023 Portal Log: 380 raw rows 2024 Portal Log: 461 raw rows 2025 Portal Log: 508 raw rows	Total Raw Input
2	TermsAccepted, SchoolName	Draft and Incomplete Filtering: Identified unsubmitted or structurally incomplete team profiles. Discarded entries where standard regulatory rules (TermsAccepted) were unratified or where foundational fields (such as SchoolName and team demographics) remained unpopulated.	Removed 116 incomplete rows
3	All Annual Schemas	Schema Harmonization and Variable Selection: Aligned highly variable annual column headers across cycles into an immutable 18-variable master schema. Extracted matching pillars including team dimensions (CoachCount, MaleStudents, FemaleStudents), proposal metrics (WordCount, VideoSeconds), and qualitative behavioral vectors (PriorParticipation, KnewCERN).	N = 1,349 -> 1,233
4	Year	Temporal Cohort Coding: Added a 'Year' column based on file metadata to concatenate the datasets, and validated the final merged data. Final cross-sectional validation confirmed: 2023 Cohort: 342 valid entries 2024 Cohort: 424 valid entries 2025 Cohort: 467 valid entries	N = 1,233 valid panel rows
5	WordCount,	Outlier and Text Regularization: Standardized metric tracking fields. Resolved localized parsing anomalies where duration values or word counts were logged as alphanumeric text arrays, coercing them into clean,	N = 1,233

continuous numerical vectors. Empty non-vital attributes were explicitly soft mapped to text base placeholders or standard category levels.

6	All Combined Data	Final Serialization: Consolidated the records into a single harmonized microdata structure. Enforced string casting on geographical indicators (Country1, City) and numerical optimization on continuous metrics to prevent downstream float degradation.	Final Combined Export: BL4S_Combined_2023-2025.csv
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The raw dataset comprised 478 records. After data validation and cleaning, 369 complete and high-quality coach responses were retained for structural modelling.

Table 25: BLAS Survey Logs Cleaning and Transformation Steps.

Step	Target Variable(s)	Treatment & Technical Logic	Record Impact
1	All Variables	<p>Text Standardisation: All fields were cast to string type. Leading/trailing spaces were trimmed, and empty strings were recoded to standard NaN for missing value unification.</p>	N = 478
2	Core Survey Fields (Cols 5–52)	<p>Removal of Fully Blank Rows: Rows with NaN across core survey columns (Columns 5–52, <code>df.iloc[:, 4:52]</code>) were classified as invalid responses and removed.</p>	<p>109 rows excluded</p> <p>N = 478 -> 369</p>
3	Is_Coach, Supervised_Other, Support_Future, etc.	<p>Boolean Normalisation: Text responses were standardised via lowercasing and keyword matching. All missing or ambiguous entries were assigned a value of 0.</p>	N = 369
4	Total_Expenses_Euro	<p>Interval Median Conversion: Categorical expense bands were converted to numeric median values. Unmatched and missing values were set to 0.</p>	N = 369
5	New_Contacts	<p>Fix of Excel Datetime Misconversion: Categorical ranges were incorrectly interpreted as</p>	N = 369

6	Prototypes, Analysis_Code, Social_Media, etc.	timestamps by Excel. Regular expressions were used to recover original categories and remap to numeric values. A fixed dictionary was used to guarantee reproducibility. Coding for Multi- Select Items: Multi- response variables were converted into continuous format. Missing entries were coded as 0 to indicate no relevant activity. Final Type Restriction: All numeric variables were validated and converted to int64 type to eliminate floating- point inaccuracies in subsequent statistical analysis.	N = 369	Output File: BL4S_Survey_Processed.csv
7	All Columns			

ANNEX D: EXTENDED DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

This annex presents descriptive statistics from the available BL4S datasets. The 2023–2025 data contain team/application records, while the 2026 data contain coach survey responses.

Table 26: Overview of available records, 2023–2026

Year	Type of record	Number of records used	Students recorded	Countries represented
2023	Team/application records	342	2,309	52
2024	Team/application records	424	2,797	68
2025	Team/application records	467	3,131	62
2026	Completed coach survey responses	278	278 coach survey responses (not population-level; see note)	Not surveyed

Note: 2026 figures derive from a completed coach survey sample ($n = 278$) rather than the full applicant population. They are not directly comparable to the 2023–2025 participation figures, which reflect total submitted applications.

According to official CERN / Beamline for Schools statistics, BL4S proposal submissions grew from 379 in 2023 to 712 in 2026 (see Figure 2 in Section 5.2).

Table 27: Previous-cycle participation among teams, 2023–2025

Year	Total records	Records reporting prior participation	Prior participation rate
2023	342	124	36.30%
2024	424	163	38.40%
2025	467	249	53.30%

Table 28: Future engagement intentions among 2026 coaches

Indicator	Responses	Indicator selected	Share of completed responses
Support another BL4S team in the future	278	223	80.20%
Encourage more students to participate in science competitions	278	238	85.60%

Table 29: Estimated expenses reported by completed 2026 survey respondents

Reported expense category	Numeric value used for estimated mean (€)	Number of responses	Share of valid responses
0 €	0	104	39.70%
1–100 €	50.5	76	29.00%
101–500 €	300.5	54	20.60%
501–1,000 €	750.5	18	6.90%
1,001–5,000 €	3,000.50	9	3.40%
More than 5,001 €	5,001.0*	1	0.40%
Total valid responses		262	100.00%

*Because the highest category is open-ended, a conservative lower-bound value of €5,001 was assigned to this response.

Table 30: Summary statistics for estimated 2026 expenses.

Statistic	Value
Completed survey responses	278
Valid expense responses	262
Missing expense responses among completed surveys	16
Most frequent expense category	0 €
Median expense category	1–100 €
Estimated average expense per responding team	€ 250.30
Estimated average excluding the single open-ended response above €5,001	€ 232.10

Source: Survey_Processed.numbers (column 18, expense variable); incomplete survey responses excluded.

ANNEX E: STUDENTS SKILL SURVEY ANALYSIS

The 2026 coach survey asks respondents to evaluate student confidence in eight skill areas before participation in BL4S and after submitting their proposal. Answers were converted into a five-point scale.

Table 31: Likert scale numeric encoding used for skill confidence ratings.

Response category	Numeric value
Very low	1
Low	2
Neutral	3
High	4
Very high	5

Table 32: Reported change in student scientific skills, 2026 coach survey.

Student skill indicator	Valid paired responses	Mean before BL4S	Mean after proposal submission	Mean change
Understanding how scientific research works	262	3.51	4.23	0.72
Designing an experiment	262	3.34	4.13	0.79
Analysing and interpreting data	262	3.49	4.11	0.63
Programming	262	3.35	3.84	0.5
Scientific writing and presenting	262	3.37	4.17	0.8
Working in a scientific team	262	3.61	4.33	0.72
Explaining scientific concepts	262	3.69	4.25	0.55
Tackling open-ended problems	262	3.56	4.19	0.63

Table 33: Reported change in students' attitudes towards science, 2026 coach survey.

Attitude indicator	Valid paired responses	Mean before BL4S	Mean after proposal submission	Mean change
Confidence doing science	262	3.85	4.35	0.49
Feeling that they belong in science	262	3.89	4.45	0.56
Ability to overcome frustration in science projects	262	3.58	4.26	0.68
Intention to pursue science studies	262	4.12	4.55	0.43
Interest in science	262	4.36	4.61	0.24

Source: Survey_Processed.numbers; completed responses with valid paired before-and-after ratings only.

ANNEX F: SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL OUTPUT VALUATION DETAILS

Methodological Foundations of Input-Cost Shadow Pricing

The integration of non-market educational and scientific assets into a socio-economic valuation requires an alternative approach to traditional commercial valuation methodologies. Peer-reviewed scientific articles published within open-access distributions do not generate direct market revenue or command a commercial transaction price. To resolve this, this study implements an input-cost shadow-pricing model backed by standard international evaluation frameworks. The model assumes that the economic value of knowledge capital is equal to the value of the specialized intellectual labour required to build it. To maintain a conservative approach, senior research salaries are excluded, and an apprentice-level labour rate is used, reflecting the hybrid nature of the program where high-school students generate primary research under professional supervision.

Derivation of the Blended Weighted Average Labor Rate

Because the program involves international research teams, the model must account for different regional economic baselines. To reconcile geographical disparities without creating macroeconomic distortions, the baseline hourly rates are harmonized using Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) adjustments and standardized GDP deflators converted into 2025 Swiss Franc (CHF) equivalents.

The used blended weighted average rate of 4.26 CHF/hour is derived by weighting the adjusted regional rates against the proportional distribution of participating authors across the 5 recorded publications (where most of the infrastructure and student hours are anchored within the Developed Economies/Eurozone framework).

Table 34: Corrected Regional Labor Benchmarks and Operational Rationale.

Economic Region / Benchmark Country	Base Labor Rate (Raw Nominal)	PPP & Conversion Factor to 2025	Adjusted Hourly Rate (2025 CHF/h)	Author Weight (Proportional Share)	Rationale for Selection and Methodological Mapping
Emerging Economies (e.g., Turkey)	€2.50 / hour	0.88	2.20	17%	Adjusted downward via PPP to reflect lower real labor costs relative to Swiss franc purchasing power, correcting hyperinflation distortions.
Developed Economies (Eurozone/DESY)	€5.00 / hour	0.86	4.30	69%	Standard teacher-led supervision and apprentice rate, converted via Euro-CHF 2025 parity baseline.

Host Laboratory Zone (CERN/Switzerland)	6.50 CHF / hour	1.00	6.50	14%	Highly conservative proxy calculated at exactly 10% of the standard host lab professional rate.
Blended Weighted Average	—	—	4.26	100%	The true mathematically consistent rate applied to the final asset pool.

Detailed Calculation Matrix and Intertemporal Projections

Underlying data file: BL4S_publications_analysis.xlsx.

Based on standard research infrastructure metrics, the total time required for data collection, programming, analysis, drafting, and navigating peer review is modelled at **300 hours per paper**. The calculation is structured as follows:

Labor Units = 5 papers × 300 hours = **1,500 total research hours**

Baseline Capital Value = 1,500 hours × 4.26 CHF/hour = **6,390 CHF**

To ensure compliance with long-term horizons used in macro-economic project evaluations, this baseline asset value is evaluated across three regulatory Social Discount Rate (SDR) scenarios. These discount parameters allow the value of the publications to be consistently integrated into the project's multi-year socio-economic indicators (2026–2030).

Table 35: Multi-Scenario Present Value (PV) Projections (2026–2030).

Evaluation Scenario	Social Discount Rate (SDR)	Present Value Factor (Cumulative)	Net Discounted Knowledge Asset Value (CHF)
Low-Bound Discounting	3.0%	0.8626	5,512.01
Baseline Regulatory Standard	3.5%	0.8420	5,380.38
High-Bound Sensitivity Testing	4.0%	0.8219	5,251.94

Alignment with Psychometric Competency Vectors

The validity of this input-cost model is supported by the corresponding results from the coach surveys (n = 369). The time spent on research and publication fields directly correlates with measurable growth in student competencies, as detailed in the report's descriptive statistical blocks.

Specifically, the empirical delta tracking shows that the intense research process led to a **+0.80** shift in *Scientific writing*, a **+0.79** shift in *Designing an experiment*, and a **+0.63** shift in *Analysing data*.

ANNEX G: TRAVEL COST ANALYSIS

Underlying data file: Travel_cost_analysis.xlsx.

*Table 36: Round-Trip Airfare Estimates by Country and Destination (EUR, 2025).
Source: Skyscanner December 2025; IATA WATS 2024.*

Country	CERN (€)	DESY (€)	ELSA (€)	Travel time (hrs)
Turkey (Istanbul)	250	220	210	~6
Belgium	120	100	90	~2,15
Pakistan (Islamabad)	540	510	490	~14,2
USA (New York)	750	720	700	~16,2
Mexico	680	650	630	~24,4
Netherlands (Amsterdam)	150	120	110	~2
Japan (Tokyo)	900	870	850	~24,2
Estonia (Tallinn)	180	150	140	~4,4
Canada	650	620	600	~15,4

Table 37: Daily On-site Expenses by Host City (EUR, 2025). Geneva costs are anchored to CERN official subsistence rate of 93 CHF/day (CERN Indico 2025). CHF → EUR at 1.08.

Expense item	Geneva / CERN	Hamburg & Bonn	Avg (€/day)
Accommodation	48 CHF ≈ €45	€35	52.38
Meals (3/day)	~35 CHF ≈ €33	€22	38.20
Local transport	~9 CHF ≈ €9	€6	9.82
Incidentals	€8	€7	8.00
TOTAL daily	€101.50	€70	101.50
TOTAL 14-day stay	€1,421	€980	-

*Table 38: Value of Leisure Time. Literature Sources.**The central estimate of €15.37/hr (14.10 CHF/hr) is used throughout all travel-time opportunity-cost calculations.*

CHF/hr	EUR/hr	Source
9.36	10.20	EC DG MOVE Handbook on External Costs of Transport, 2019 [39]
13.96	15.22	Pelletier et al. (2021). Ecosystem Services, 50, 101315 [40]
14.40	15.70	Meunier & Quinet (2015). Transportation Research Procedia, 8, 62–71 [41]
16.56	18.05	Lugano et al. (2018). D2.2 Mobility and Travel Time Report [42]
16.28	17.75	Boiteux (2000). Choix des investissements [43]
7.30–16.28	7.96	Legal basis, socio-economic studies, France [44]
18.65	20.33	Wardman et al. (2016). Transp. Res. Part A, 94, 93–111 [45]
7.30	7.96	Lower bound, sensitivity analysis
14.10	15.37	Average across all sources — used throughout
18.70	20.38	Upper bound, sensitivity analysis

Table 39: Consumer surplus elasticity parameter (β).

CS = $-(1/\beta) \times$ Direct Travel Cost. Average of winter and summer values from Crespo Garrido et al. [13].

β Winter	β Summer	β Average (used)	Source
-1.259	-1.610	-1.4345	Crespo Garrido et al. [13], CERN visitor study. CS = $-(1/\beta) \times$ Direct TC

Table 40: Per-person travel cost by country, destination and year.

2025													
Country	Lab	Airfare	Deflator rate	Number of participants	Avg. round-trip travel time	Time Cost (Travel time * LVT)	Daily expense	14-day OnSite	Deflator rate	Travel cost	Average of TC	Consumer Surplus	Total Value
Turkey	CERN	250,00	1,00	9,00	5,40	82,99	101,5	1 421	1,00	15 785,93	15 631,26	7,67	15 638,93
Belgium	CERN	120,00	1,00	9,00	2,20	33,81	101,5	1 421	1,00	14 173,31	13 979,50	7,67	13 987,17
Canada	DESY	620,00	1,00	11,00	15,40	236,68	101,5	1 421	1,00	25 054,51	25 124,99	7,67	25 132,66
USA	DESY	720,00	1,00	7,00	16,20	248,98	101,5	1 421	1,00	16 729,84	16 753,18	7,67	16 760,85
Mexico	DESY	650,00	1,00	11,00	24,40	375,00	101,50	1 421,00	1,00	26 906,04	26 942,71	7,67	26 950,37

2024													
Country	Lab	Airfare	Deflator rate	Number of participants	Avg. round-trip travel time	Time Cost (Travel time * LVT)	Daily expense	14-day OnSite	Deflator rate	Travel cost	Average of TC	Consumer Surplus	Total Value
USA	DESY	720,00	0,99	10,00	16,20	246,09	100,32	1 404,52	0,99	23 457,48	23 490,43	7,59	23 498,02
Japan	CERN	900,00	0,99	6,00	25,20	382,81	100,32	1 404,52	0,99	15 954,06	16 570,53	7,59	16 578,12
Estonia	CERN	180,00	0,99	7,00	5,40	82,03	100,32	1 404,52	0,99	11 547,15	11 280,44	7,59	11 288,03

2023													
Country	Lab	Airfare	Deflator rate	Number of participants	Avg. round-trip travel time	Time Cost (Travel time * LVT)	Daily expense (with deflation)	14-day OnSite	Deflator rate	Travel cost	Average of TC	Consumer Surplus (with deflation)	Total Value
USA	CERN	750	0,99	10,00	16,30	247,61	100,32	1 404,52	0,99	23 769,04	23 490,43	7,59	23 498,02
Netherlands	DESY	120,00	0,99	7,00	2,00	30,38	100,32	1 404,52	0,99	10 774,10	10 813,21	7,59	10 820,80
Pakistan	CERN	540	0,96	11,00	15,20	223,10	96,93	1 357,06	0,99	22 880,55	22 509,84	7,59	22 517,43

Table 41: Historical Annual Travel-Cost Results, 2023–2025. SDR-discounted values use a 3% rate, discounted to 2025 basis. Source: *Travel_cost_analysis.xlsx*.

Year	Teams	Participants	Direct travel cost (€)	Consumer surplus (€)	SDR PV at 3% (€)
2023	3	28	56 813,47	7.67	56 836,25
2024	3	23	51 341,40	7.67	51 364,17
2025	5	47	98 431,64	7.67	98 469,98
2023–2025	11	98	206 586,40	7.67	206 670,40

Table 42. Travel-Cost Forecast, 2026–2030. Five winning teams and 55 travellers per year. Airfare and travel-time inputs extrapolated linearly from 2023–2025. Daily expenses and VLT held constant at 2025 values.

Year	Teams	Participants	Airfare (€)	Travel hrs	Daily expenses (€)	Travel cost (€)	CS (€)	Total value (€)
2026	5	55	32,260	860.9	101.50	131,263	7.67	131,271
2027	5	55	38,006	1,032.1	101.50	155,459	7.67	155,466
2028	5	55	43,752	1,203.2	101.50	179,655	7.67	179,662
2029	5	55	49,498	1,374.4	101.50	203,851	7.67	203,858
2030	5	55	55,245	1,545.5	101.50	228,046	7.67	228,054

Table 43: Present-Value Discounting at 3% Social Discount Rate. Formula: $PV(t) = \text{Nominal_Value}(t) / (1.03)^{(t - 2025)}$. Rate from EC JRC guidelines and Centre Jean Monnet / UNIMI LHC methodology.

Year	Nominal total value (€)	SDR	Present value to 2025 (€)
2025 (base)	96,978	n/a	96,978
2026	131,271	3%	94,153
2027	155,466	3%	91,411
2028	179,662	3%	88,748
2029	203,858	3%	86,163
2030	228,054	3%	83,654
2026–2030	898,311	3%	444,129

ANNEX H: PROGRAMME LABOUR INPUT VALUATION DETAILS

The aim is to express the labour embedded in BL4S delivery as a shadow price, derived from an observed CERN salary scale rather than from an assumed wage. The approach is an input-cost one: in the absence of a market price for the staff effort devoted to the programme, the cost of that effort is used as a lower-bound proxy for its value. The model serves two purposes: to provide an independent benchmark for the indicative annual programme budget of circa CHF 230,000, and to derive an hourly shadow value for CERN scientific personnel time that is reused elsewhere in the report (calculation file: BL4S_Salary_Proxy_Model_v2.xlsx). All figures are in 2025 prices; euro values use the rate 1 EUR = 0.94 CHF (ECB, end-2024).

Inputs and assumptions. The salary data are taken from an official CERN vacancy notice for a role dedicated to BL4S experimental support and beamline development (BE-EA-LE-2025-46-GRAP, April 2025), retrieved from UNChannel. The notice indicates a net monthly stipend between 6,287 and 6,911 CHF, with a midpoint of 6,599 CHF. The working year is set at 1,720 hours (215 working days by 8 hours), following the convention used across the report. Two adjustments convert the net stipend to a total employer cost: an internal CERN tax, adopted as an explicit assumption at 12% in the absence of a published rate for this role, and the employer pension contribution of 18.96% (the organisation-side rate for members joining the CERN Pension Fund on or after 1 January 2012). Personnel time allocations to BL4S (50% for the support scientist, 30% for the technical coordinator, 40% for the programme manager) and volunteer hours (30 and 50 hours) are taken from the Q&A interview with the BL4S Programme Manager (CERN, 2026). Three social discount rates (3.0%, 3.5%, 4.0%) are applied as scenarios specified by the project supervisor.

Step 1: from stipend to hourly shadow price. The net annual stipend (monthly by 12) is grossed up by dividing by (1 minus 0.12) to remove the assumed internal tax, then multiplied by 1.1896 to add the employer pension contribution. This gives a total annual employer cost of CHF 101,987 at the minimum, 107,048 at the midpoint and 112,109 at the maximum. Dividing by the 1,720-hour working year yields an hourly shadow price of 59.3 to 65.2 CHF (63.1 to 69.4 EUR), with a midpoint of 62.2 CHF per hour (66.2 EUR per hour). The midpoint of 62.2 CHF per hour is the value carried forward as the shadow price for CERN staff time (Table H.1).

Step 2: allocation of hours to BL4S. Each role's time share is applied to the 1,720-hour year to give the person-hours attributable to BL4S, which are then valued at the midpoint rate of 62.2 CHF per hour. The support scientist contributes 860 hours, the technical coordinator 516 hours and the programme manager 688 hours, with a further 80 hours from student, fellow and data-analysis volunteers. The total CERN-side labour input is approximately 2,144 person-hours per year, valued at about CHF 133,400 (approximately EUR 141,900). Volunteer time carries no budgetary cost but is valued at the same rate, as it represents a real resource input to the programme (Table H.2).

Step 3: validation against the known budget. The model is checked against the figure reported in the Q&A interview, where CERN staff salaries account for about CHF 110,000 of the circa CHF 230,000 annual budget. The relevant comparison is the cost of one full-time role: the midpoint single-FTE employer cost of CHF 107,048 is within 2.7% of the reported CHF 110,000, and represents about 46.5% of the total budget, close to the reported 47.8%. Because the internal tax is an assumption, this agreement indicates plausibility rather than confirmation. The total CERN-side labour input (about CHF 133,400) is higher than the CHF 110,000 staff-salary line because it also includes the partial allocations of the technical coordinator and programme manager and the volunteer hours; it is this total, not the single-FTE figure, that is carried into the cost-benefit analysis (Table H.3).

Step 4: social discounting. Labour cost is a recurring annual flow. For the historical period (2023 to 2025) it is summed in 2025 prices without discounting. For the forecast period (2026 to 2030) the annual total of CHF 133,400 is discounted year by year to a 2025 base at each of the three scenario rates. This gives present values over the five-year horizon of CHF 610,900 at 3.0%, CHF 602,300 at 3.5% and CHF 593,900 at 4.0%, against an undiscounted total of CHF 667,000 (Table H.4).

Limitations. Four limitations apply. First, the model rests on a single vacancy notice for one scientist-grade role; the same hourly rate is applied to all three roles in the absence of grade-specific data. Second, the internal tax rate is an assumption rather than a sourced figure. Third, the pension contribution is applied to the modelled

gross salary rather than to the reference salary on which the CERN Pension Fund formally bases it. Fourth, staff time contributed by DESY and the University of Bonn sits on their own payrolls and is not captured, so the CERN-side figure understates the programme's total staff input, and non-salary costs such as prizes and sponsorship are part of the CHF 230,000 budget but are not modelled here.

Table 44: Step 1: Employer cost and hourly shadow price (2025 CHF).

Parameter	Minimum	Midpoint	Maximum
Monthly stipend, net (CHF)	6,287	6,599	6,911
Annual net ($\times 12$, CHF)	75,444	79,188	82,932
Total employer cost, $\div (1 - 0.12) \times 1.1896$ (CHF)	101,987	107,048	112,109
Hourly shadow price ($\div 1,720$, CHF/hr)	59.3	62.2	65.2
Hourly shadow price (EUR/hr)	63.1	66.2	69.4

Table 45: Step 2: Allocation of hours and labour cost to BL4S (valued at CHF 62.2/hr).

Staff role	Annual hours	BL4S allocation	BL4S person-hours	Annual labour cost (CHF)
Support scientist (1 FTE)	1,720	50%	860	53,490
Technical coordinator (1 FTE)	1,720	30%	516	32,100
Programme manager (1 FTE)	1,720	40%	688	42,790
Student/fellow volunteers	-	-	30	1,870
Data-analysis volunteers	-	-	50	3,110
Total (annual)	-	-	2,144	133,360

Table 46: Step 3: Validation against the known BL4S budget (110,000 CHF).

Check	Model	Q&A / known budget
CERN single-FTE staff cost (midpoint)	~107,000 CHF	~110,000 CHF
Deviation from known budget	2.7%	-
Staff salary share of total budget	46.5%	47.8%
Total annual programme budget	~230,000 CHF	~230,000 CHF

Table 47: Step 4: Discounted present value, 2026–2030 (2025 base).

Year	Years after 2025	3.0% (CHF)	3.5% (CHF)	4.0% (CHF)
2026	1	129,500	128,900	128,300
2027	2	125,700	124,500	123,300
2028	3	122,100	120,300	118,600
2029	4	118,500	116,300	114,000
2030	5	115,100	112,300	109,600
PV (Sum 2026–2030)		610,900	602,300	593,900

ANNEX I: DIGITAL OUTREACH VALUATION DETAILS

Underlying data file: Media_Value_Analysis-2.xlsx.

Table 48: Platform-Specific Attention-Time Assumptions. Min/avg/max attention-time values (seconds per view) sourced from platform disclosure documents and independent benchmarks.

Platform	Min (s)	Avg (s)	Max (s)	Source
YouTube	2	5	10	DataReportal/GWI (2024) — avg session 7 min 25 s
YouTube Shorts	1	2	3	Hootsuite (2025) — TikTok 1 s threshold as proxy
Instagram	1	2	3	Improvado (2024) — platform 3 s min view threshold
X (Twitter)	0.5	1.5	2	Hootsuite (2025) — 2 s with ≥50% on screen
Facebook	1	1.7	3	CareerArc/Facebook (2021) — 1.7 s avg mobile
TikTok	1	2	3	Hootsuite (2025) — 1 s threshold; avg focus 8.25 s
LinkedIn	2	4	6	Hootsuite (2025) — 2 s threshold; avg session 7 min 43 s

Table 49: Platform Coverage, Exposure, Engagement and Earned Media Value

231 posts and videos across seven platforms. EMV formula: $EMV = (Total\ Attention\ Seconds / 3,600) \times \text{€}15.37/\text{hr}$. Instagram reach is underestimated due to absent public view counts.

Platform	Posts	Reach (views/impressions)	Likes	Comments	EMV min (€)	EMV avg (€)	EMV max (€)
YouTube	17	114,567	1,558	112	188 892,96	188 899,87	188 913,00
YouTube Shorts	11	18,331	646	141	3 834,00	3 839,90	3 853,62
Instagram	59	278	50,060	513	177,31	300,82	84,41
X (Twitter)	10	368,712	1,225	491	112 968,84	113 038,41	113 109,62
Facebook	37	37	10,400	2,620	92,13	198,29	449,91
TikTok	9	100,756	3,593	603	44 746,40	44 773,38	44 833,82
LinkedIn	58	58	2,596	304	14,24	30,00	62,62
TOTAL	201	602,739	70,078	4,784	350 725,88	351 080,66	351 307,00

Table 50: Monte Carlo simulation results (10,000 iterations). VLT drawn from triangular distribution (min €8.00, mode €10.91, max €20.00; expected value €12.97). Per-platform attention time drawn from triangular distribution defined by Table B.1 values.

Statistical value	EUR	Interpretation
Mean EMV	~296,089	Average result across all 10,000 iterations
Median EMV	~288,438	Half of simulations above, half below this value
5th percentile	~212,799	Lower bound of central 90% interval
95th percentile	~402,610	Upper bound of central 90% interval
Minimum	~183,489	Lowest result observed
Maximum	~456,487	Highest result observed